

Running Head: Self-Determination Theory in Sport

Self-Determination Theory in Sport:

Differences between Athletes in Individual and Team Sports

Tiffany Callahan

Dr. Angela Bryan

Dr. Renee Magnan

University of New Mexico – Albuquerque

Abstract

Using a Self-Determination Theory (SDT) framework, this study examined the relationships between needs satisfaction and motivation and possible differences in these relationships for athletes in individual versus team sports. Participants were 260 college athletes from the University of New Mexico. Autonomy ($r = .23, p < .001$), relatedness ($r = .36, p < .001$), and competence ($r = .12, p = .046$) predicted intrinsic motivation among athletes. As predicted, amotivation was found to be negatively related to autonomy ($r = -.29, p < .001$), competence ($r = -.18, p = .003$), and relatedness ($r = -.19, p = .002$). Needs satisfaction measures were similar except for autonomy $t(258) = 3.019, p < .010$, which was higher for individual athletes. There was a not a sport by needs satisfaction interaction which indicated a similar pattern of intrinsic, $p = .94$ versus extrinsic motivation, $p = .91$ by type of sport (team or individual).

Self-Determination Theory in Sport: Differences between Athletes in Individual and Team Sports

It takes something special to make an individual want to get up early in the morning, often before the sun rises and go for a three hour run. It takes even more for that athlete to go out before the sunsets and do it again. Whether it is the individual athlete that focuses the majority of their time training and competing alone, or members of a team that train and compete together, all types of athletes are driven. This driving force that gets athletes out of bed early in the morning and helps inspire them to train through numerous injuries is motivation. This driving force is so strong that it has often been the focus of many studies (Kingston, Horrocks, & Hanton, 2006; Thøgersen-Ntoumani & Ntoumanis, 2006). Some researchers have suggested that the foremost reason that motivation in sport is often studied is because athletes are highly motivated by differing types of motivation: external and internal (Vallerand, Deci, & Ryan, 2006; Vallerand & Losier, 1987, 1994). However, being that there are different kinds of athletes who compete in sports, it is logical to propose that there are also differing dynamics that motivate these individuals. A theory that is often used to interpret the differing kinds of motivation that an individual experiences is that of Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

Self-Determination Theory

Self-Determination Theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2000) outlines the conditions that either assist or hinder the natural processes of healthy psychological development (i.e., well-being) and self-motivation (i.e., intrinsic motivation). Specifically, Deci & Ryan (2000) speculate that an individual's potential for success is based on personality assimilation and an innate need and desire to grow. People who are intrinsically motivated will engage in the most self-determined

behavior, and it is self-determined behavior that fulfills underlying needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. These terms will be discussed in detail later in this paper. The presence or absence of these three needs determines whether an individual has optimal social functioning and performance (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Wilson & Rodgers, 2002). SDT has often been applied to the domains of education, exercise regulation, and sports (Amorose, 2003; Edmunds, Medic, Wilson, & Starkes, 2007; Ntoumanis, & Duda, 2006; Tauer & Harackiewicz, 1999; Wilson & Rodgers, 2002). For example, exercise regulation can be seen by encouraging participants to attend personal training and then practice skills they learn outside of the gym. Those individuals who have their needs satisfied are more likely to be intrinsically motivated and are therefore more likely to continue to exercise on their own. Within sports, SDT makes predictions about success based on whether athletes' psychological needs are enhanced or restricted.

Currently, little is known about how motivation differs between individual and team athletes. Specifically, little is known about how SDT applies to individuals that are a part of a team. Given that the social context of a team might be more consistent with extrinsic motivations and decreased autonomy (wanting to do well "for the team" as opposed to for oneself) and more consistent with fulfilling relatedness needs. It seems reasonable to expect that self-determination processes might differ between people participating in individual versus team sports. In this study, SDT will be used to examine motivation and need fulfillment in sport and how they differ between team and individual sport athletes.

Psychological Needs and Motivation

SDT identifies three psychological needs as being important and fundamental to an individual's motivational environment: competence, autonomy and relatedness (Vallerand,

Pelletier, & Koestner, 2008). Competence is the extent to which an individual believes that he or she is effective at getting desired results in a given setting and are confident in their abilities to achieve their goals (Woods, Bolton, Graber, & Crull, 2007). For example, an athlete that not only understands a complex play, but then can go out and successfully carry it out is likely to have a high amount of competence. In general, people who are more competent are usually more driven or autonomous. Autonomy is an individual's self-driven, self-regulated internal desire to do something. An individual is autonomous if he or she has control over the choice of what to do and if that choice comes from internal regulation (e.g., an internal sense of control over an activity). Autonomy also leads to higher overall levels of intrinsic motivation (Motl, 2007). Lastly, relatedness is the need to feel socially interconnected to others and it has been found that people should seek out connections with others (Baumeister & Leary, 1995). These needs are extremely important and predictive of the style of motivation that one may possess. If any of the needs for competence, relatedness, and autonomy are not met, negative consequences may occur, such as a decrease in motivation (Woods, Bolton, Graber, & Crull, 2007). As mentioned before, these different needs are indicative of the nature of motivation that is portrayed by individuals. SDT proposes that there is more than one type of motivation an individual can possess and these types lie within a continuum.

Continuum of Motivation

SDT identifies three very different types of motivation (i.e., intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation; Kowal & Fortier, 1999) which all fall along a continuum. Figure 1 illustrates the continuum of motivation as described by Ryan & Deci (2000) in their theory of SDT. It shows how each regulatory style of motivation along with its corresponding regulatory style. Where an individual falls along the continuum is directly related to their personal

satisfaction of the previously specified psychological needs. On one end are people who are motivated by internal factors (intrinsic motivation). Deci & Ryan (2000) suggest that true intrinsic motivation is the highest and most self-determined form of motivation that an individual can possess. Positive feedback and communication that increase feelings of competency and autonomy will also increase intrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Intrinsic motivation is the natural desire within an individual to attain and accomplish something that an individual finds personally enjoyable. In the middle of the continuum lies extrinsic motivation, extrinsically motivated individuals often engage in behaviors for an outside reward like a medal or cash incentive. On the opposite end of the spectrum from intrinsic motivation is amotivation. Amotivated individuals have a complete lack of motivation -- usually stemming from a complete lack of competence (Motl, 2007). There are regulatory styles of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation that are important to and identified by SDT that contribute to an individual's overall motivation.

Figure 1. The social-determination theory continuum of motivation.

The three important regulatory styles of intrinsic motivation identified by Vallerand & Rousseau (2001) are intrinsic motivation toward knowledge, accomplishment and external

stimulation. Intrinsic motivation towards knowledge can be seen when an athlete engages in a sport because of the joy he or she gets from learning and accomplishing something new. For example, a soccer player might enjoy going to practice because he or she likes learning new plays. Intrinsic motivation towards accomplishment occurs when an athlete becomes excited when he or she breaks a previously set personal record. For example, a track athlete might be thrilled to break a previous 100-meter time. Intrinsic motivation towards stimulation can be seen when an individual engages in an activity because of the excitement and thrill they feel while participating. For example, this can be seen when an individual goes downhill biking and traverses down very steep mountains for feeling that they get in their stomach from doing it.

There are three different regulatory styles of extrinsic motivation that reflect progressively more external motivation: external regulation, introjected regulation, and identified regulation (Deci & Ryan, 2000). External regulation (i.e., extrinsic motivation) occurs when people engage in activities to get an award or to avoid punishment -- they have minimal self-determination and autonomy (Deci & Ryan, 2000). A football player who only plays because he wants everyone to know that he is a good player is externally regulated. Introjected regulation occurs when people engage in an activity to avoid feeling guilty or to boost their egos (Deci & Ryan, 2000). A woman who goes to the gym because it makes her feel better about herself is exhibiting introjected regulation. Finally, identified regulation involves valuing a behavioral goal (i.e., the action is personally important; Deci & Ryan, 2000). For example, a baseball player may decide to lift weights to improve his or her pitching arm. The athlete is working towards a goal that is not directly important, but will improve his or her overall game.

The last type of motivation and the one that is found on the opposite end of the continuum from intrinsic motivation is amotivation. Amotivation involves a lack or absence of

motivation and a belief that a desired outcome is not possible to achieve (Thogersen-Ntoumani & Ntoumani, 2006). People who are amotivated believe that they cannot control the outcomes of their behavior and as a result simply refuse to try, thereby illustrating a complete lack of competence. For example, basketball players often spend many hours practicing in order to improve their skills and to ultimately get more playing time – by practicing they believe they have control over whether they are good enough to play. However, if they practice a lot and do not then get any additional play time, they may experience amotivation. That is, they may feel useless and experience amotivation towards practicing and playing well.

Figure 1.

Cohesion & Cooperation

Much of the work that has been done with SDT and intrinsic motivation in sports has focused on an individual's needs and motivations (Deci & Ryan, 2000) without much attention to important aspects of the sport context in which these motivations occur for different types of athletes. Behavior is a result of the constant interaction between the person and the situation, and understanding this interaction requires looking at the characteristics of the situation in addition to the characteristics of the person. When investigating the context of sports participation, two important aspects are cooperation and competition (Blanchard, 1995). Cooperation refers to a group of individuals working together to achieve a mutual goal whereas competition involves one person trying to outperform other individuals (Duetsch, 1949; 1962 in Tauer & Harakiewicz, 2004). Tauer and Hackiewicz (2004) have found that cooperation can have positive and negative effects on performance. When competition poses an appropriate challenge to the individual it can result in excitement and increased intrinsic motivation. Cooperation, on the other hand, may cause individuals to feel less autonomous because they are viewed as being part of a group or

team and no longer as an individual. This point illustrates just how delicate the balance between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can be in a cooperative or team situation. While it makes sense to believe that a team environment ought to be a strong force for increasing relatedness needs (Tauer & Harackiewicz, 2004) it may be that the characteristics of the team determines the success of the team environment. Cooperation is not the only factor that has been highlighted as important in success for team success; cohesion has also been discussed as an important aspect to cooperative sports (Landers, Wilkison, Hatfield, & Barber, 1982). In fact, Carron, Brawley, and Widmeyer (1985) argue that the more cohesive a team can be or become, the better their overall performance will be.

Carron and Chelladurai (1981) define cohesion as activities whose primary goal is enhancement of group maintenance. In general, the more cohesive a team, the more likely the team will be successful and the more intrinsic motivation the members of the team will have. The cohesion of a group is dependent upon many factors, but most surround individual feelings and needs of the members in the group. For example, two players on a hockey team may show cohesiveness when they demonstrate a play for the team. In this scenario, the two players can either work together or compete against each other. If they compete against each other, they could take longer to demonstrate the play and also run the risk of performing the play incorrectly. Individuals on a team and the leaders of the team must make decisions about whether or not to work together and how to work together in the most efficient way.

Males, Kerr, Thatcher, and Bellew (2006) investigated an elite men's volleyball team's challenge to successfully work as a cohesive unit and how failing to do so led to disappointing results. Specifically, they assessed five team members' responses to failure. The study found that the team's inability to play successfully caused them to morph from a successful unit to a group

of unsuccessfully individuals. Males et al. suggested that the team may have been unsuccessful because of a lack of communication between the players and a lack of a consistent team process and structure. Communication can help members of a team feel more like a cohesive group versus a group of individual players. Lack of communication can cause a unified team to feel unrelated, illustrating the damaging effect that can result from diminished team cohesion. Males and colleagues also analyzed conversations between players and found that the players did not communicate like a successful team, but rather like many individual players. The findings from this study suggest that without cohesion a group can have little hope of success. Because each member feels that their results are controlled by the other team members, they became “demotivated” (Males et al, 2006). In other words, team members begin to feel that external factors maybe controlling the situation instead of their individual efforts and feel that there was nothing they could do to change the situation. In extreme cases, a team that lacks cohesion can cause amotivation as a result in its members.

Another study by William and Widemeyer (1991) looked at the relationship between cohesion and performance among 83 NCAA Division I female collegiate golfers. The golfers completed questions on cohesion using the Group Environment Questionnaire (GEQ; Carron et al. 1985). Results indicated that cohesion was positively related to greater performance in sports where athletes must work together -- illustrating how powerful cooperation and cohesion can be on the success of athletes in a given domain. The positive effects of cohesion and cooperation are not the only effects that have been analyzed in regards to success in sports. The negative effects of cooperation have also been frequently studied.

SDT looks at individuals' success in sport as dependent upon one's ability to fulfill innate psychological needs. Individual-sport athletes compete against themselves to be successful

whereas team-sport athletes compete against themselves and other team members to be successful (Stanne, Johnson, & Johnson, 1999). However, for a team to be successful, the team members must also work together to enhance cooperation and cohesion. In contrast, for an individual to be successful, cooperation and cohesion are not particularly important, and they may be less vulnerable to extrinsic motivational factors (e.g., pressure from teammates to win) undermining their intrinsic motivation. Thus, intrinsic motivation and autonomy may be more difficult to achieve in team versus individual sports. In particular, individual versus team athletes use different the different strategies towards fulfilling their needs and becoming intrinsically motivated: Individual athletes are more likely to meet their needs through autonomy and competence, whereas team athletes are more likely to meet their needs through relatedness.

Current Study

The present study examined the differences in motivation between athletes in individual sports and athletes who are part of an athletic team. In particular, we addressed three hypotheses:

- (1) Athletes in team sports will have significantly higher extrinsic motivation for participation in their sport than athletes in individual sports. Specifically, this will be manifest in extrinsic motivation in the areas of external, introjected and identified regulations, and in amotivation.
- (2) Athletes in team sports will have significantly lower intrinsic motivation for participation in their sport than athletes in individual sports. Specifically, higher levels of intrinsic motivation toward knowledge, accomplishment, and stimulation should be seen in individual-sport athletes. To the extent that athletes display intrinsic motivation, the

intrinsic motivation of team athletes will be the result of higher levels of relatedness than athletes in individual sports, whereas the intrinsic motivation of individual athletes will be the result of higher levels of competence and autonomy than those on a team.

- (3) Low cohesion among team-sport athletes will be related to higher levels of amotivation, whereas high cohesion will be related to higher levels of intrinsic motivation amongst team athletes.

Method

Participants

Participants were 260 (140 male and 120 female) NCAA college athletes who averaged 21 years of age ($SD= 3.78$, age range: 18-25). Participants were volunteers from eleven teams at The University of New Mexico. Athletes participating in team sports totaled 103 athletes and consisted of five teams: baseball ($n=45$), soccer ($n=21$), softball ($n=11$), volleyball ($n=14$), and women's basketball ($n=12$). Athletes in individual sports totaled 157 athletes on six teams: cross-country running, ($n=30$), golf ($n=23$), skiing ($n=17$), swimming ($n=25$), tennis ($n=22$), and track and field ($n=40$).

Design

This study was a two-group between-subjects design comparing athletes in team sports to athletes in individual sports. The researcher acknowledges that this study is essentially a nested design in which athletes are nested within teams; therefore not all the observations are independent. Additional analyses within this type of design would indicate whether there may be differences that exist between different teams and not just between individual athletes and team

athletes. For the purpose of the current thesis, the independent variable will be type of sport (i.e., team or individual sport). There are three categories of dependent variable: types of motivation (three types of intrinsic, four types of extrinsic, and amotivation), need satisfaction (autonomy, competence, and relatedness), and, for team sports, cohesion.

Procedure

The investigator approached all of the sports teams at The University of New Mexico during the 2008-2009 school year to participate in the current study. Out of the 13 sports teams approached about participating in the study only two declined participation: Men's basketball and women's soccer.

After giving informed consent, questionnaire packets were administered to athletes at one of their practices. Participation was completely voluntary and anonymous, and there were no rewards or compensation given to athletes that chose to participate. The total time for athletes to complete the different parts of the study took approximately 20 minutes.

Measures

The questionnaire packet contained three separate measures: a questionnaire to establish the participants' demographics, a questionnaire to assess motivation, and one to assess cohesion.

Demographics.

A demographics questionnaire was used to identify several characteristics of the participants, including age, sex, race and ethnicity.

Present and Future Motivation.

The *Sports Motivation Scale* (SMS; Pelletier, Fortier, Vallerand, Briere, & Blais, 1995) evaluated the types of motivation athletes use during sport participation. This scale has seven subscales measuring intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation. Three types of intrinsic motivation were assessed (motivation to know, motivation to accomplish things, and motivation to experience sensation), an example item is “for the pleasure I feel in living exciting experiences,” $\alpha=.89$. The three types of extrinsic motivation were assessed (external motivation, identified motivation, and introjected regulation), an example item is “because it is absolutely necessary to do sports if one wants to be in shape”, $\alpha=.76$. An example measure of amotivation is “I used to have good reasons for doing my sport, but now I am asking myself if I should continue doing it,” $\alpha=.83$. Participants responded to each statement by indicating how much it corresponded to them on a 7-point scale (1=does not correspond at all to 7= corresponds exactly).

Cohesion. To measure cohesion amongst the athletes, the 18-item *Group Environment Questionnaire* (GEQ; Carron, Widemeyer, Brawley, 1985) was used. These items assess how attractive a group is to its members and how attractive and integrated a group or team appears to an individual. An example question is “I do not enjoy being a part of the social activities of this team.” Responses were provided on a 9-point scale (1= strongly disagree to 9= strongly agree), $\alpha=.82$.

Needs Satisfaction. To measure relatedness, a 10-item scale from the *Feelings of Relatedness Scale* (Richer & Vallerand, 1998) was used. For example, participants were asked “In my relationships with the members of my sport team, I feel supported.” Responses were made on a 7-point scale with lower scores indicating a lower sense of relatedness and higher scores reflecting higher relatedness, $\alpha=.96$. Competence was measured using three items developed by Amorose (2003). For example, “How good do you think you are at your sport?”

Responses were made on a 5-point scale with higher scores indicating more competence, $\alpha=.84$. To measure autonomy, a 5-item scale from Hollembeak and Amorose (2005) was used. For example, "I have a say in what I do when participating in my sport." Responses were made on a 5-point scale (1= not at all true for me to 5= completely true for me), $\alpha=.75$.

Results

To analyze the differences that may exist between individual and team athletes, t-tests were used for group comparisons.

Descriptive Statistics

The majority of the 260 athletes were juniors ($n=78$) followed by freshman ($n=76$), seniors ($n=53$), sophomores ($n=48$), and those having more than four years of college ($n=5$). Of these participants, 77% were Caucasian, 14% Hispanic, 7% African-American, 3% Asian, 2% other and 1% were Native American. There were a total of 82 (34.2%) team athletes and 158 (65.8%) individual sport athletes.

Needs Satisfaction

Table 1 shows the relationships between satisfaction, motivation, and cohesion. Measures of needs satisfaction: autonomy ($r = .23, p < .001$), relatedness ($r = .36, p < .001$), and competence ($r = .12, p = .046$). Contrary to predictions, relatedness was not related to extrinsic motivation ($r = .08, p = .19$), while autonomy was negatively correlated ($r = -.12, p = .06$). As predicted, amotivation was inversely related to autonomy ($r = -.29, p < .001$), competence ($r = -.18, p = .003$), and relatedness ($r = -.18, p = .002$).

Table 1. The Relationship between Needs Satisfaction, Motivation, and Cohesion.

	Intrinsic Motivation	Extrinsic Motivation	Amotivation	GEQ
Competence	.12*	.010	-.182**	-.001
Relatedness	.36**	.084	-.185**	.628**
Autonomy	.23**	-.117	-.29**	.420**

Note. * $p > .05$, ** $p > .01$.

Needs Satisfaction Differences by Sport

Table 2 shows the mean differences in needs satisfaction between sports type. A series of *t*-tests were run to identify differences in needs satisfaction between type of sport. There were no significant differences found between individual sport and team sport athletes in relatedness, $p = .19$ or competence, $p = .196$. However, a significant difference was found for autonomy between sport type such that team athletes had lower autonomy ($M = 3.45$) than individual athletes ($M = 3.75$), $t(258) = 3.02$, $p < .01$.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviations for Needs Satisfaction Measures by Type of Sport.

	Individual <i>M (SD)</i>	Team <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Autonomy	3.74(.80)	3.45(.68)	.003
Competence	4.07(.64)	4.17(.59)	.196
Relatedness	5.52(1.24)	5.32(1.03)	.187

Motivation

Table 3 shows the mean difference in kind of motivation and cohesion by type of sport. No intrinsic or extrinsic motivational differences were found between team and individual athletes, $ps = .94$ and $.91$, respectively, nor any differences in amotivation between type of sport, $p = .84$. Thus, both individual and team athletes did not have differing levels of amotivation – suggesting that both types of athletes are equally motivated to compete in their sport. Figure 2

shows the distribution of specific means for each team for intrinsic, extrinsic, amotivation, and cohesion. The figure identifies specific differences between each team, but was not something that was specifically measured it does however; provide an accurate description of differences between specific teams.

Table 3. Means and standard deviations for Motivation type by type of sport.

	Individual <i>M (SD)</i>	Team <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> -value
Intrinsic Motivation	5.31(.95)	5.29(.84)	.94
Extrinsic Motivation	3.78(.94)	3.77(.78)	.91
Amotivation	2.04(1.21)	2.01(1.03)	.84
GEQ	7.09(1.05)	6.93(1.05)	.23

Figure 2. Motivational Differences Between Different Sports Teams.

Domains of Motivation

Table 4 shows the means and standard deviations for the different regulatory styles of motivation by type of sport. The specific sub-types within extrinsic and intrinsic motivation also showed no differences between individual and team sports. Specifically, none of the three forms of intrinsic motivation (i.e., motivation towards knowledge, towards satisfaction, and towards external stimulation) were significantly different between individual and team athletes ($ps = 1.00, .75, \text{ and } .59$, respectively). In addition, the three forms of extrinsic motivation measured (i.e., external regulation, introjected regulation, and identified regulation) were not significantly different between individual and team athletes ($ps = .08, .14, \text{ and } .62$, respectively). These results suggest that athletes possess similar forms of motivation regardless of type of sport.

Table 4. Means and standard deviations for regulatory styles of motivation by type of sport.

	Individual <i>M (SD)</i>	Team <i>M (SD)</i>	<i>p</i> -value
<i>Intrinsic Motivation</i>			
Knowledge	4.96 (1.25)	4.96 (1.11)	1.00
Accomplishment	5.52 (.92)	5.56 (.88)	.75
Stimulation	5.44 (1.02)	5.38 (.86)	.59
<i>Extrinsic Motivation</i>			
External Regulation	4.21 (1.82)	4.36 (1.24)	.48
Introjected Regulation	4.12 (1.45)	3.86 (1.24)	.14
Identified Regulation	4.87 (1.21)	4.96 (1.03)	.62

Cohesion

As with motivation, no differences were found for cohesion between individual and team athletes and cohesion, $p = .83$, indicating that group and team athletes had reported similar

cohesion. The means of this test imply that individual athletes had non-significantly, but slightly higher cohesion than that of team athletes, which was an unexpected result and not originally predicted.

Discussion

The main purpose of the present investigation was to examine the motivational differences that may exist between individual and team athletes. Specifically, the relationship between fulfillment of needs satisfaction, motivation, and group cooperation were assessed. According to SDT, athletes who are more intrinsically motivated or self-determined are more likely to be successful in their sport. Individual athletes should, in theory, have an easier time being intrinsically motivated than that of team athletes, due to the fact that they only have themselves to worry about. Whereas, in a group setting if an individual feels that they do not have control over their individual results or feels like they lack cooperation with their team members they are not likely to be successful or intrinsically motivated (Males et al., 2006).

Extrinsic Motivation

Contrary to hypotheses, differences in motivation were not found between team and individual athletes. Hypothesis 1 stated that team athletes should have higher extrinsic motivation than individual athletes. Results indicated that team and individual athletes reported similar levels of extrinsic motivation, suggesting that both individual and team, athletes were equally motivated for external reasons regardless of the type in which they participate (Chantal, Guay, & Dobreva-Martinova, 1996). Hypothesis 1 also stated that team athletes would score higher than individual athletes on certain forms of external motivation. These forms of extrinsic

motivation were identified regulation, introjected regulation, and external regulation and individual and team athletes did not differ on their reported levels of these three forms of extrinsic motivation.

Both types of athletes also had similar levels of amotivation. Amotivation is defined as a complete lack or absence of motivation. This finding is counter to what we know about motivation among athletes. In accordance with research on cooperation, team athletes should have higher amotivation than individual athletes because their results are dependent upon the teams overall success and not an individual effort (Chantal, Guay, Dobreva-Martinova, & Vallerand, 1996).

Intrinsic Motivation

Hypothesis 2 stated that individual athletes should have significantly higher intrinsic motivation than team athletes. In contrast to this hypothesis, athletes had similar amounts of motivation regardless of type of sport. Hypothesis 2 also stated that individual athletes would score higher than team athletes on certain forms of internal motivation. These forms of intrinsic motivation are intrinsic motivation towards knowledge, accomplishment, and towards external stimulation. Individual athletes again showed no significant differences on any of these constructs compared to team athletes suggesting that individuals in this study may not be engaging in sports for different reasons and as a result can be motivated by both intrinsic and extrinsic reasons (Anderson-Butcher, Newsome & Ferrarii, 2003; Weiss & Ferrer-Caja, 2002 in Amorose & Anderson-Butcher, 2007).

Hypothesis 2 also stated that individual athletes would have higher competence and autonomy, whereas team athletes would have higher levels of relatedness. Differences were found in needs satisfaction between individual and team athletes. Consistent with this hypothesis,

individual athletes had did report higher levels of autonomy than team athletes did; however, no differences were found between sports type for competence or relatedness. These findings suggest that individual athletes are having their needs of autonomy met more so than team athletes. Again, autonomy is an individual's self-driven reason for doing something. An athlete that has high autonomy is likely to feel in control of their own results and because of this have higher motivation. A study by Gagne, Ryan, & Bargmann (2003) showed the effects of autonomy support and how having high amounts of autonomy is conducive to continual motivation. Team athletes, in contrast to hypotheses were not found to have significantly higher levels of relatedness than individual athletes, and they were shown to have similar levels of extrinsic motivation as individual athletes. A possible explanation of this can be supported, Males et al. (2006), ran a study in which their results supported that an athlete that does not feel he/she has open cohesion or cooperation will feel less relatedness towards other team members and in-turn, this should result in an overall decrease in intrinsic motivation for that athlete.

Cohesion

The final hypothesis stated that lower levels of cohesion should be related to higher levels of amotivation. In contrast to this hypothesis, no differences in amotivation were found between the two types of athletes. Again, amotivation occurs when an athlete feels that they have no control over the outcomes of their effort (Deci & Ryan, 2000), this is a common occurrence amongst athletes that do not feel they have cooperation and open communication amongst their team mates. This is a finding that would be expected according to SDT and group cohesion research.

The lack of motivational differences between individual and team athletes was surprising. One explanation is that if an athlete is motivated and wants to do well, the type of sport is

inconsequential. Another explanation is that individuals self-select into the sports that are a good physical and psychological fit, and thus are best suited to meet their needs. Perhaps, SDT may not be the best theory to analyze how motivation works in an elite group of athletes. There may be a more complex relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation that is not looked at closely enough in this theory. The theory does an excellent job of providing intricate details of how needs satisfaction and motivation are intertwined and reliant upon each other, however, it may be too reliant on this relationship. It is possible that athletes could be successful without having their needs met and because they are successful, they are motivated. In other words, maybe the relationship is more intertwined, maybe it is entirely situational or completely “feeling” based. If needs satisfaction attainment is based upon an individual’s belief of having their specific needs met, and every individual is different, it is difficult to find one model that can incorporate enough aspects to appease everyone’s needs.

The limitations of this study lie primarily within the population itself. The number of team to individual athletes could not be matched due to the fact that two teams at the university did not agree to participate. Another limitation is that although motivation was measured, performance was not. A measure of performance would have provided detailed insight into intrinsic motivation and performance amongst college athletes. This would be increasingly important because it would validate assumptions about motivation if we could prove that it is linked to success. A major limitation to this study is in the design itself, mainly, because it is a cross-sectional study. It would be a stronger study if it were longitudinal. We could measure motivation at the beginning of the year and measure performance at the end of the year. This would provide stronger evidence for the effects of motivation on performance.

Future research should focus on how motivational styles impact athlete performance. This is important because of the large impact that coaching can have on an athletes training and success. If more research is done on the effects of motivation and performance then we can change and modify coaching strategies. Perhaps more coaches can provide the type of support that is most conducive to success and in turn, produce more successful athletes. Additionally, future research should address these motivational styles among high school and middle school athletes. When athletes are young they are only beginning to learn their sports and developing training habits. As previously mentioned, once we can better identify the factors that limit and enhance an individual's motivation in sport we can better help these athletes to achieve their goals.

Conclusion

The findings from this study are not in direct support of SDT and show the need for an additional model in the realm of sports. Athletes are complex beings and it maybe that they are motivated by numerous undiscovered reasons. In order to better understand what drives these athletes, more research needs to be done. Again, although motivation within sports is just a small part of overall motivation, it is still important. More knowledge in this area can provide more detail and understanding into what motivates human beings and this alone can help us to understand how to modify and improve health related behaviors in every realm.

References

- Amorose, A.J. (2003). Reflected appraisals and perceived importance of significant others Appraisals as predictors of college athletes' self-perceptions of competence. *Research for Exercise and Sport, 74*, 60-70.
- Amorose, A.J. & Anderson-Butcher, D. (2007). Autonomy-supportive coaching and self-determined motivation in high school and college athletes; a test of self-determination theory. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise, 8*, 654-670.
- Baumeister, R. & Leary, M.R. (1995). The need to belong: desire for interpersonal attachments as a fundamental human motivation. *Psychological Bulletin, 117*, 497-529.
- Bird, A.M. (1977). Team structure and success as related to cohesiveness and leadership. *The Journal of Social Psychology, 103*, 217-223.
- Blanchard, K. (1995). *The anthropology of sport: An introduction — A revised edition* (2nd ed.). Westport, Connecticut: Bergin & Garvey Publisher, Inc.
- Carron, A.V. & Chelladuri, P. (1981). The dynamics of group cohesion in sport. *Journal of Psychology, 3*, 123-139.
- Carron, A. V., Widemeyer, W.N., Brawley, L.R. (1985). The development of an instrument to assess cohesion in sports teams: The group environment questionnaire. *Journal of Sport Psychology, 7* (3), 244-266.
- Chantal, Y., Guay, F., Dobreva-Martinova, T., & Vallerand, R.J. (1996). Motivation and elite performance: An exploratory investigation with Bulgarian athletes. *International Journal of Sports Psychology, 27*, 173-182.
- Deci, E.L. & Ryan, R.M. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist, 55*(1), 68-78.
- Edmunds, J., Ntoumanis, N. & Duda, J. (2006). A test of self-determination theory in the exercise domain. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology, 36*(1), 2240-2265.
- Gagne, M., Ryan, R.M., & Bargmann, K. (2003). Autonomy support and need satisfaction in the motivation and well-being of gymnasts. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology, 15*, 372-390.
- Hollembek, J. & Amorose, A.J. (2005). Perceived coaching behaviors and college athletes' intrinsic motivation: a test of self-determination theory. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology, 17*, 20-36.

- Kingston, K. M., Horrocks, C. S., & Hanton, S. (2006). Do multidimensional intrinsic and extrinsic motivation profiles discriminate between athlete scholarship and status and gender? *European Journal of Sport Science*, 6, 53-63.
- Kowal, J. & Fortier, M.S. (1999). Motivational determinants of flow: contributions from self-determination theory. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 139, 355-368.
- Landers, D. M., Wilkison, M. O., Hatfield, B. D., & Barber, H. (1982). Causality and the cohesion-performance relationship. *Journal of Sport Psychology*, 4, 170-183.
- Males, J.R., Kerr, J.H., Thatcher, J.H., & Bellew, E. (2006). Team process and players' psychological responses to failure in a national volleyball team. *The Sport Psychologist*, 20, 275-294.
- Medic, N., Mack, D.E., Wilson, P.M., Starkes, J.L. (2007). The effects of athletic scholarships on motivation in sport. *Journal of Sport Behavior*, 30(3), 292-306
- Motl, R.W. (2007). Chapter 2: theoretical models for understanding physical activity behavior among children and adolescents-social cognitive theory and self-determination. *Journal of Teaching and in Physical Education*, 26, 350-357.
- Pelletier, L.G., Fortier, M.S., Vallerand, R.J., Tusson, K.M., Briere, N.M., & Blais, M.R. (1995). Toward a new measure of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation in sports: The Sport Motivation Scale. *Journal of Sports & Exercise Psychology*, 17, 35-53.
- Richer, S. & Vallerand, R.J. (1998). Construction and validation of the validation of the Perceived Relatedness Scale. *Revue Europeene de Psychologie Appliquee*, 48, 129-137.
- Stanne, M., Johnson, D., & Johnson, R. (1999). Does competition enhance or inhibit motor performance: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125, 133-154.
- Tauer, J.M. & Harackiewicz, J.M. (1999) Winning isn't everything: competition and achievement orientation, and intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 35, 209-238.
- Tauer, J.M. & Harackiewicz, J.M. (2004). The effects of cooperation and competition on intrinsic motivation and performance. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 86(6), 849-861.
- Thøgersen-Ntoumani, C. & Ntoumanis, N. (2006). The role of self-determined motivation in the Understanding of exercise-related behaviours, cognitions and physical self-evaluations. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 24 393-404.

- Vallerand, R. J. , Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1987). Intrinsic motivation in sport. *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews, 15*, 389-425.
- Vallerand, R. J. & Losier, G. F. (1994). Self-determination and sportsmanship orientations: an Assessment of their temporal relationship. *Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology, 16*, 365-404.
- Vallerand, R.J., Pelletier, L. G., & Koestner, R. (2008). Reflections on Self-Determination Theory. *Canadian Psychology, 49*, 257-262.
- Vallerand, R.J. and Rousseau, F.L. (2001) Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in sport and exercise: A review using the hierarchical model of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. In: *Handbook of Sport Psychology*. Eds: Singer, R.N., Hausenblas, H.A. and Janelle C.M. 2nd edition. New York: John Wiley & Sons. 389-416.
- Williams, J. M. & Widemeyer, W. N. (1991). The cohesion-performance outcome relationship In a coating sport. *Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology, 13I*, 364-377.
- Wilson. P.M. & Rodgers, W.M. (2002). The relationship between exercise motives and physical self-esteem in female exercise participants: an application of self-determination theory. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Research, 7*, 30-43.
- Woods, A.M., Bolton, K.N., Graber, K.C., & Crull, G.S. (2007). Chapter 5: influences of Percieved motor competence and motives on children's physical activity. *Journal of Teaching and in Physical Education, 26*, 390-403.